

“Using Memory Strategies To Enhance EFL Grammar To 1st University Level”

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 18, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Memory, Mnemonics, Cognitive, Imagery, Rehearsal, Elaboration</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4618533</p>	<p><i>This study investigates the impact of using memory strategies to enhance the learning of grammar to pre university level students. There are different memory strategies considered as tools to strengthen the memory because information is sometimes easy to remember and easy to forget so therefore this study is basically concerned with particular memory techniques that are very useful for students to memorize the new grammatical items that have been given for the first time. The participant of this study were 20 male and female EFL learners of pre university level who underwent a hour of instruction by Google Classroom, there were randomly divided into an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was directly taught how to perform memory strategies in learning grammar. The post-tests were conducted to collect the required data through using multiple choices questionnaires. The results showed that the experimental group's learnt grammatical items retention statistically improved moreover there is a significant statistical difference between the two groups.</i></p>

Introduction

Research Question

1. Can memory strategies impact on the learning of EFL grammar?
2. What are the memory strategies used on grammar enhancement of EFL learners in pre university level?
3. How are the memory strategies are used?
4. What are their effects on the learning of EFL Grammar?

2. Problem statement

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of using memory strategies to enhance EFL grammar.

3. Hypothesis

The memory strategies will be applied to enhance the learning of EFL grammar and they will play positive role in retrieving and recalling grammatical items .

There will be a mean difference in the scores obtained by the participants in both experimental control and groups.

4. Theoretical Background

In fact, Memory strategies are a special type of cognitive operation. Although different researchers define strategies slightly differently, they are generally conceived as mentally effortful, goal-directed process that are adopted to enhance memory performance. Strategies are controllable and are performed deliberately by the individual and are probably available to consciousness. Strategies are basically related with other cognitive operations and are influenced by many factors. (Courage & Nelson, 2009, p2).

Oxford (1990) developed language learning strategy system, which includes the two main classification: direct strategies and indirect strategies.

Direct strategies are specific ways that involve use of language that directly involve the target language. All direct strategies require mental processing of the language.

Figure 1. Classification of learning strategies (Oxford: 1990)

They are sub-divided into Memory, Cognitive and Compensation and our immediate concern in this paper is memory strategies and how to use them to enhance the teaching of EFL grammar.

Memory strategies Sometimes called mnemonics, they are clearly more effective when the learner simultaneously uses metacognitive strategies like paying attention and affective strategies, like reducing anxiety through deep breathing.

Memory strategies often involve pairing different types of material. In language learning, it is possible to give verbal labels to pictures, or to create visual images of words or phrases, linking the verbal with visual is very useful to language learning for four reasons:

First: the mind's storage capacity for visual information exceeds its capacity for verbal material.

Second: the most efficiently packaged chunks of information are transferred to long-term memory through visual images.

Third: visual images may be the most potent device to aid recall of verbal material.

Fourth: a large proportion of learners have preference for visual learning.

The second Oxford's (1990) classification of learner strategies is indirect strategies. These strategies can be divided into metacognitive, affective and social strategies. Metacognitive strategies help learners control their "cognition" and "coordinate" their learning through "centering", "arranging", "planning" and "evaluating". They include three strategy groups: centering your learning; arranging and planning your learning; and evaluating your learning (p. 137).

Oxford (1990) defined affective strategies as the techniques that enable learners to control feelings, motivations and attitudes related to language learning (p. 71). She identified three major sets of affective strategies: lowering your anxiety, encouraging yourself, and taking your emotional temperature. According to Oxford, lowering anxiety can be achieved through using progressive relaxation, deep breathing, or meditation; using music; and using laughter. Encouraging yourself, However, you can take your emotional temperature through listening to your body, using a checklist, writing a language learning diary, and discussing your feelings with someone else (pp. 140, 141).

According to Oxford (1990), social strategies are the skills that help learners to "facilitate interaction with others, often in a discourse situation" (p. 71). She outlined three sets of social strategies: asking questions, cooperating with others, and emphasizing with others. Asking questions can be in the form of asking for clarification, verification or correction. However, cooperative strategies involve cooperating with peers and with proficient users of the new language.

According to Oxford (1990), Memory strategies fall into four sets and each set has a number of strategies.

a. Creating Mental Linkages.

It involves the strategies of grouping, association and placing new words into a context

b. Applying images and sounds.

It involves the strategies of imagery, semantic mapping, using keywords and representing sounds in memory

c. **Reviewing well.**

It can be achieved through the strategy of structured reviewing

d. **Employing acting.**

It is related to the strategies of using physical response or sensation, and using mechanical technique

In order to enhance grammar learning or any language aspects, there should be memory strategies, such as elaboration, mental imagery, mnemonics, organization, and rehearsal, which are helpful in retrieving information. (Santrock, 2011; Schunk, 2012; Woolfolk, 2013).

Elaboration. Is the addition of distinctiveness to new information exemplifies the strategy of elaboration. Woolfolk (2013) explained that elaboration helps in encoding and retrieval of new information because it links new information to older information.

Mental imagery. The use of Visualizing images of verbal information lead to the construction of mental imagery. The dual coding theory (Paivio, 1971) states that memory for linguistic information is enhanced if relevant imaginal information is activated, and such activation of both verbal and nonverbal systems results in the dual coding of information.

Mnemonics. The Imagery and words can be combined as mnemonics to assist memorization. There are various types of mnemonic strategies: rhymes (e.g., “righty tighty, lefty loosey”), spelling rules (e.g., “*i* before *e* except after *c*”), song lyrics (e.g., “head and shoulders, knees and toes”), phrases (e.g., use “never eat soggy waffles” to remember the compass directions “north, east, south, and west”), acronyms (e.g., use “HOMES” to remember the five Great Lakes – Huron, Ontario, Michigan, Erie, and Superior), method of loci (e.g., use the logical movement after supper to remember “a tiger” on the countertop, “a monkey” in the sink, “a hippo” in the dishwasher, and “a bald eagle” on the sofa), keyword method (e.g., connect vivid images of two apples getting married to remember “Annapolis is the capital of Maryland”).

Organization. The connection of items to one another can organize information in such a way that recalling one item also recalls other items linked to it. Santrock (2011) explained that organization makes large amounts of information more manageable and more meaningful. Woolfolk (2013) recommended the use of hierarchy to integrate pieces of information, the use of chunking to group information into higher-order units to be remembered as single units, or the use of outline to organize information.

Rehearsal. ongoing rehearsing information over and over can somewhat slightly extend the length of time it stays in memory. Santrock (2011) stated that rehearsal works best when encoding and remembering of a list of items for a brief period of time, but it does not work well when for retaining information over the long term. Woolfolk (2013) also mentioned that rehearsal works well with highly overlearned material, such as multiplication facts, spelling words, or a play script, but it does not work well for remembering more complex and meaningful information. In spite of the fact that a human mind is capable of storing around 100 trillion pieces of information, we cannot have access to this huge storage without employing memory strategies (Oxford 1990, p. 38). Hence, the present study demonstrated the effect of using memory strategies, particularly "applying images and sounds", and "employing acting" on students EFL learners' ability to recall the grammatical items, present simple and past simple, use auxiliaries and adjectives to describe things and part of speech.

5. Literature review

The purpose of this section is to review the literature related to language learning strategies in general, and memory strategies in particular. Although, there are many studies on using memory strategies in developing vocabularies but there is a big gap that English language teaching lacks studies on using memory strategies in enhancing learning EFL grammar. Only few studies have been conducted to use some memory strategies for grammar enhancement.

Heuer (1999) indicated that in order for the new information to be transmitted from short-term memory to long-term memory, it has to be related with a schema that already exists in memory. This depends on two "variables": the extent to which the new information is related to the schemata and the amount of processing given to the new information (pp. 23, 24). However, he added that if the new information does not "fit" any existing structure or schema in the memory, then we should use to mnemonic devices to "commit" information to the memory.

Such studies on memory strategies in classrooms focus on how teachers use these strategies. Pressley, Allington, Wharton-McDonald, Block, and Morrow (2001) noted that teachers' instruction of memory strategy is lacking in the intensity necessary for students to learn how to use memory strategies effectively. In addition, Ornstein,

Coffman, and Grammer (2009) found that teachers vary considerably in how much they use memory-relevant language, such as strategies and metacognitive questions (questions related to students' knowledge of how memory works) that encourage students to remember information.

Although learning is important, retention and recall of the items learnt should not be underestimated. Language items retention refers to the ability of recalling or remembering things after a period of time has passed. "In language teaching, retention of what has been taught (e.g. grammar rules and vocabulary) may depend on the quality of teaching, the use of different memory strategies, the interest of the learners, or the meaningfulness of the materials" (Richards & Schmitt, 2002, p. 457).

According to Solso (1995), memory strategies (mnemonics) are tools or devices, either verbal or visual in nature, that serve to improve the storage of new information, and how the information retained in memory to be recalled. Mnemonics have been proven to be extremely effective in helping students remember things. If the information is shown in a way correlates meaningfully to what is already known, then it will be stored for relatively long periods of time and thus retrieval through verbal or visual clues becomes quite easy. In other words, by using memory strategies or mnemonic strategies, teachers can relate new information to what have already been stored in their long-term memory.

Thompson (1987) similarly acknowledging the usefulness of mnemonic devices by stating that they can help learners learn faster and recall better by integration of new material into existing cognitive units and by providing retrieval cues. Mnemonic devices are proved to be effective in all ages. They are, however, more useful for low level students because they are involved mostly in activities requiring them to remember and recall information (Levin, 1993).

It can be noted that memory strategies, as one of the most effective strategies in the learning EFL Grammar and they are extremely powerful mental tools. Oxford (1990: 38) states that the mind can store some 100 trillion bits of information, but only part of that potential can be used unless memory strategies come to the aid of the learner. Using memory strategies generally involves in associating different types of material. That's why, they are helpful in learning grammatical items and remembering them in the long term.

Oxford (1990) defined LLSs as "operations employed by the learner to aid the acquisition, storage, retrieval, and use of information" (p. 8). Later, she extended this definition to include "specific actions taken by the learner to make learning easier, faster, more enjoyable, more self-directed, more effective, and more transferable to new situation" (ibid, p. 8). However, Weinstein and Mayer (1986) indicated that LLSs are "behaviors and thoughts" that learners engage in while learning and which influence the learners' "encoding process" (p. 60).

According to Chamot (1987), LLSs are "techniques, approaches or deliberate actions that students take in order to facilitate the learning and recall of both linguistic and content area information" (p. 71).

Schmitt (1997) defined memory strategies (mnemonics) as strategies that involve relating the word with some previously learned knowledge by using some form of imagery or grouping (p. 216). Macaro (2001) pointed out that MSs work by "processing" words or vocabulary items in the "working memory" so that it can be stored and retrieved from the long-term memory. He added that the strategies adopted for retrieving the piece of language will be similar to the way it was stored (p. 118).

In this paper, I would like to shed the light on important role of memory strategies in enhancing the process of Learning new items of grammar and how to be recalled as quickly as possible. The points are target of learners, teachers' role, memory enhancement technique and tools, and procedure of teaching which are connected one to another bounded in one package of teaching process.

6. Methodology.

A. Research design

This study followed an experimental design in which two groups were selected randomly and a pre test has been conducted to recognize the initial background knowledge of the two groups as well as post test has been conducted to get the required data.

B. Participants.

The participants of both groups have randomly been selected from the University of Babylon, College of Basic Education, they were all from 1st level, but different genders. The total number of participants is 20 students, 10 students each group.

C. Instruments / materials

The instruments and materials were being used are tests, online lectures and multi questions questionnaire for both the control and experimental groups and then we collected the data in order to be analyzed to determine how independent variable can impact on dependent variable and also to answer research questions.

Twenty pre university level EFL learners have participated in this study implemented on Google classroom. All of them were adult female and male students selected randomly .

D. Procedure

This study was conducted in three phases :

Phase one: it is a pre-test, the participants were tested before using the memory strategies in the class. The purpose behind this is to know the background knowledge of the students. The time was allocated for this phase is thirty minutes. It included 10 questions to each group and a question carries (1 M).

Phase two: In this phase, the participants of the two groups were given a lesson, the control group was given a presentation without using any memory strategies and it wasn't given any special treatment. In contrast, the experimental group was given a presentation using the particular memory strategies like applying acting, applying image and sound and mnemonics. The allocated time for this phase is an hour.

Phase three: It is delayed post test. The independent variable was the impact of using memory strategies in teaching grammar and dependent variable was the learners' EFL grammar retention. A week later, the participants were tested in order to get the results of the study and to see if there is a significant difference between the two groups. So the test included 25 questions were given to both groups.

Both classes were held consecutively by using Power Point Presentation, the class was about the teaching of the simple and present tense, uses of auxiliaries and adjectives to describe something, and explaining the cause and effect clauses.

Group A is the experimental group. It was taught by applying memory strategies (applying images and sounds and employing acting) so the subjects got acquainted with the concept of strategy through presentation including the brief definitions of the two kinds of memories and example to clarify them. Items were given differently in each kind of strategy and group B was the control group has been taught without using any effective memory strategies only repetition strategy.

Data analysis

Firstly, The findings of the study were analyzed both descriptively and statistically. SPSS program (Version 20) was used to analyze the data which have been obtained from instruments (pre test and post test). Consequently, we started analyzing the data of pre tests of both groups in order to realized the background of both control and experimental groups so we observed the data are relatively similar and there was no significant difference between them before applying the treatment.

Experimental	2	2	3	2	3	4	2	3	3	4
control	3	2	2	1	2	3	4	4	2	1

Table (1).The results of pre tests

Group Statistics

EXPERIMENTAL	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
CONTROL 1.00	10	2.4000	1.07497	.33993
2.00	10	2.4000	1.07497	.33993

Then, the results of the post tests should be analyzed across two groups, experimental and a control, in order to measure how far the independent variable (memory strategies) effects on the dependent variable (grammar learning) as well as to answer the research question.

NO	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Experimental	5	6	6	5	7	9	7	7	7	9
Control	5	4	4	3	5	5	4	6	4	3

Table (2) The results of post test.

Group Statistics

	VAR00001	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Posttest 1.00		10	6.8000	1.39841	.44222
2.00		10	4.3000	.94868	.30000

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
								Lower	Upper	
Postest	Equal variances assumed	.775	.390	4.678	18	.000	2.50000	.53437	1.37732	3.622
	Equal variances not assumed			4.678	15.836	.000	2.50000	.53437	1.36622	3.633

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Postest	20	3.00	9.00	5.5500	1.73129
VAR00001	20	1.00	2.00	1.5000	.51299
Valid N (listwise)	20				

After submitting data to SPSS, and using t-test , Independent sample test was conducted to compare the possible differences between the means of experimental and control groups based on the obtained scores from the post-tests. We observed that there is a significant difference so the mean in the experimental group is (5.5) and is (1.5) for control group and the standard deviation is (1.7)for experimental group and (.5129) for control group.

Conclusion

The present study focused on the implementation of memory strategies in EFL classes and reported on the learners' performance on grammatical items retention tests. It also considered the relationship between students' memory and the grammar items retention. The findings of the present study help us obtain knowledge on the appropriate application of memory strategies in EFL classes. Analysis of statistical results revealed that the experimental and control groups were different regarding the mean scores in the post test meaning that the using of memory strategies can impact on EFL grammar learning. Consequently, it can be said that there is a meaningful difference between teaching based on traditional strategies and teaching based on memory strategies in students' grammar learning retention.

References:

- Chamot, A. U. (2004). Issues in language learning strategy research and teaching. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching, 1*, 14-26. Retrieved March 20, 2011, from <http://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/v1n12004/chamot>.
- Heuer, R. J. (1999). *Psychology of intelligence analysis*. Washington DC: Centre for the Study of Intelligence.
- Levin, J. R. (1994). Memory strategies and classroom learning: A twenty-year report card. *The Elementary School Journal, 94*, 235-244.
- Macaro, E. (2001). *Learning strategies in second and foreign language classrooms*. London: Continuum.
- Nelson, D.L., & Quick, J.C. (2009). *Organizational Behavior: Science, the Real World and You*, 6th (Ed.). Mason, OH: Southwestern/Cengage
- Oxford, R.L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
- Paivio, A. (1971). *Imagery and verbal processes*. New York: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.
- Santrock, J. W. (2011). *Educational Psychology*. (5th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill
- Schmitt, N. (1997). Vocabulary learning strategies. In N. Schmitt & M. McCarthy (Eds.), *Vocabulary: description, acquisition and pedagogy* (pp.199-228). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Scruggs, T. E., Mastropieri, M. A., Berkeley, S. L., & Marshak, L. (2010). Mnemonic strategies: Evidence-based practice and practice-based evidence. *Intervention in School and Clinic, 46*, 79-86
- Sheorey, R. & Mokhtari, K. (2001). Differences in the metacognitive awareness of reading strategies among native and non-native readers. *System, 29*, 431-449.

- Song, M. J. (1998). Teaching reading strategies in an ongoing EFL university reading classroom. *Asian Journal of English Language Teaching*, 8, 41–54.
- Robert L. Solso. Allyn and Bacon, 1995 *Cognitive Psychology*. 4th edition, England.
- Thompson, I. (1987). Memory in language learning. In A. Wenden & J. Rubin (Eds.), *Learner strategies in language learning* (pp.43-56). Cambridge: Prentice-Hall.
- Thompson, I. (1987). Memory in language learning. In A. Wenden & J. Rubin (Eds.), *Learner Strategies in Language Learning*.
- Weinstein, C., & Mayer, R. (1986). The teaching of learning strategies. In M. C. Wittrock (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teaching* (pp. 315-327). New York: Macmillan.
- Woolfolk, A. E. (2013). *Educational Psychology*. (12th ed.). Boston: Pearson.

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